

ANALYSIS OF ARCHITECTURAL DECISIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

The article examines architectural decisions in software development and their impact on system performance, with a focus on microservice architecture (MA). Aspects such as scalability, fault tolerance, security and the impact on system response time are analyzed. The article explores the principles of microservice autonomy and independence, their advantages over monolithic architecture, as well as potential issues related to network delays and data consistency. Deployment and monitoring automation tools that help optimize the performance of microservice systems are discussed.

Keywords: microservice architecture (MA), scalability, fault tolerance, security, system performance, monitoring, network delays.

Introduction

Architectural decisions play a critical role in the development of modern information systems, as they determine not only the internal structure and interaction of components but also affect scalability, performance, fault tolerance, and the potential for further system evolution. With the rapid growth of data, increased demands for processing speed, and the need for quick adaptation to business changes, choosing the right architecture becomes especially important. Architectural mistakes can lead to reduced performance, scaling difficulties, and increased system maintenance costs.

In recent years, microservice architecture (MA) has gained widespread adoption due to its ability to enhance system flexibility and scalability. Unlike traditional monolithic architectures, microservices allow a system to be divided into independent components, enabling parallel development, deployment, and scaling. This is especially relevant for large companies and projects that require high performance and the ability to

quickly adapt to changing market conditions. The relevance of microservices is driven by the need for greater flexibility in software development and improved collaboration between development teams. Their use allows for the quick implementation of new features, avoiding system downtime and reducing the risks associated with code changes. The goal of this article is to conduct a comprehensive analysis of architectural decisions with a focus on MA, as well as to evaluate their impact on the performance, scalability, and flexibility of modern systems.

Main part. Description of MA. Comparison with monolithic architecture

The approach to software development, where an application is broken down into many small, independently deployable services, is called MA. Each microservice performs one or more business functions and interacts with others through lightweight protocols, such as HTTP (HyperText Transfer Protocol) or AMQP (Advanced Message Queuing Protocol), as shown in picture 1.

Pic. 1. Model MA [1]

This type of architecture is based on several principles that ensure its effectiveness and flexibility. One of them is **autonomy**, which means that each microservice is an independent functional unit that performs its task without the need for close interaction with other services. Each microservice manages its own data,

business logic, and resources, which minimizes dependencies between system components. The autonomy of services allows them to be independently developed, scaled, and deployed. This also reduces system complexity overall, making it more modular and resilient to failures in individual components.

Another advantage of MA is the **ability to independently deploy individual services**. This means that each microservice can be updated or scaled without affecting other system components, minimizing downtime and risks associated with new version deployments. This feature simplifies the implementation of new features since changes in one service do not require modifications in others. This principle also supports DevOps practices such as continuous integration and continuous deployment, accelerating the development and release cycle of new versions.

Loose coupling refers to minimizing the number of dependencies between microservices. Each microservice interacts with others through well-defined interfaces and standardized protocols (such as REST or

gRPC). This reduces inter-service dependencies and allows for internal changes within a microservice without affecting other parts of the system [2]. These principles form the foundation of MA and enable the creation of flexible, scalable, and fault-tolerant systems that can evolve and change according to business needs without requiring a complete system overhaul.

Since MA is one of the most popular approaches to building modern software systems, it is important to compare it with traditional monolithic architecture for a complete understanding of its advantages and disadvantages (table 1).

Table 1

Comparative analysis of architectural decisions [3, 4]

Aspect	Microservice architecture	Monolithic architecture
The structure of the system	The system consists of many independent services.	All components are integrated into one single application.
Scalability	Scaled by individual services (horizontal).	Scaling requires cloning the entire application.
Development independence	Each team can work on a separate service.	Coordinated work on a single code base is required.
Deployment independence	Updates and changes can be applied to individual services.	The entire application needs to be restarted when the code changes.
Technology stack	It is possible to use different technologies for different services.	Limiting the use of a single set of technologies
Fault tolerance	Failure of one service does not lead to failure of the entire system.	Failure of any component can lead to failure of the entire system.
Development time	Rapid implementation of changes in individual services.	Long-term implementation, testing of the entire system is required.

Comparative analysis shows that each approach has its own strengths and weaknesses that must be considered when choosing an architectural solution for a specific project. The microservice option offers greater flexibility in development, scalability, and independent deployment of components, making it suitable for large distributed systems. At the same time, monolithic architecture is simpler to manage and provides higher performance within a single process, but it can face challenges when scaling and implementing changes, especially as the system grows. The choice between these approaches should be based on the project's needs, size, scalability requirements, and long-term development considerations.

Analysis of the impact of architectural decisions on system performance

The impact of architectural solutions on system performance is expressed in such important aspects as latency, scalability, fault tolerance and security. In modern systems, especially in the context of MA, these aspects play an important role in ensuring stable and efficient operation. Architectural decisions directly **affect system latency and response time**, particularly in MA, where each component interacts with others over the network. This is significantly different from monolithic applications, where components interact directly within a single process. Network communications between microservices can lead to increased delays compared to in-process calls in monoliths. To minimize

this, it is necessary to choose efficient data transfer protocols, such as gRPC (which is faster than REST), reduce the volume of transmitted information, and strive to decrease the number of inter-service calls through approaches like request aggregation or data caching.

In MA, distributed transactions are widely used, requiring the application of complex patterns such as Saga. These patterns provide transaction management in distributed systems, ensuring the execution of operations or their cancellation in case of errors. However, this adds additional delays and can reduce system performance, as each transaction requires coordination between multiple services, each of which must confirm or roll back changes [5]. To reduce the impact on performance, methods like eventual consistency are often used, which allow temporary discrepancies in data between services, enabling faster transaction processing.

Scalability and fault tolerance are crucial aspects for any system, especially under increasing load. One of the most significant advantages of MA is its ability to scale horizontally, i.e., the ability to scale individual system components by increasing the number of service instances. This allows flexible responses to load changes without the need to modify the entire system. It is also important to consider tools like Kubernetes or Docker Swarm, which manage microservice scaling at the container level. They automatically increase or decrease the number of service instances depending on the current load, ensuring efficient resource usage.

The use of MA enhances system fault tolerance, as failures in one microservice do not affect the operation of other services. Unlike monolithic systems, where an error in one component can take down the entire system, in microservices, a failure can be localized in a single service, which can be restarted or replaced without affecting other parts of the system. This is achieved due to the independence of services from one another and their ability to function autonomously.

Microservices can be automatically restarted in case of failure. Container management systems like Kubernetes have built-in monitoring and automatic service recovery mechanisms. If one of the services stops working, it automatically restarts or is replaced. In microservices, fault tolerance is ensured by using redundancy and service duplication. For example, multiple instances of the same service can run in parallel, distributing the load and reducing the likelihood of failure. The use of circuit breaker patterns (protection from cascading failures) also helps prevent errors from spreading throughout the system, limiting failures to individual services.

Microservices introduce new risks for **data security**, as each service can interact with others over the network. This creates potential vulnerabilities for data interception or unauthorized access, especially if proper communication security is not ensured. To protect data between microservices, approaches such as the following must be used:

- Data encryption implies that all data transmitted between services must be encrypted using modern encryption standards, preventing data interception or tampering during transmission.
- Data protection at the storage level means that microservice systems must ensure data encryption not only during transmission but also at the storage level (e.g., in databases and file systems).
- Multi-level authentication means that every connection between services must be secured with authentication and authorization mechanisms to prevent unauthorized data access [6].

Access management in MA becomes more complex because each service can have its own authentication and authorization system. To centralize access management and avoid inconsistencies, it is necessary to use standardized protocols such as OAuth 2.0, OpenID Connect, and JWT tokens (JSON Web Tokens).

Architectural decisions applied in systems based on microservices significantly affect parameters such as latency, scalability, fault tolerance, and security. Optimizing MA performance requires the use of various tools and technologies for system management, automation, and monitoring.

Continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) automation is an essential part of MA, allowing for faster delivery of updates and reducing system downtime. This helps development teams to make frequent and safe changes to the code without disrupting the system, which is especially important in MA, where each component can be updated independently. Effective microservice monitoring is necessary to ensure their

performance. Collecting data on service status and visualizing it allows for quick responses to issues, identifying bottlenecks, and predicting failures. Modern monitoring tools integrate with orchestration systems, providing developers and administrators with detailed reports and metrics on the performance of each microservice. Microservice orchestration is the management of their deployment, scaling, and fault tolerance. Under dynamic load conditions, which may fluctuate depending on user activity, orchestration systems automatically manage resources, distributing requests between services and ensuring uninterrupted operation. This enhances system flexibility and reduces the risk of failures. Data caching and efficient request routing play an important role in optimizing microservice performance. Caching reduces the load on services since frequently requested data can be provided faster, and request routing ensures their directed distribution between services, which reduces response time and improves the overall system performance.

These technologies and approaches contribute to the creation of flexible and high-performance microservice systems capable of handling large loads and quickly adapting to changes. However, to effectively implement microservices, it is important to consider the specifics of individual projects and businesses. Best practices demonstrate their effectiveness in examples of major companies that have successfully implemented MA and achieved significant improvements in system performance and flexibility.

One such example is **Netflix**, which was one of the first major technology players to transition from monolithic architecture to microservices. This allowed the company to scale its platform, serving millions of users worldwide, and ensure high content availability even during peak loads. Netflix uses orchestration based on Kubernetes and actively applies monitoring tools such as Prometheus and Grafana to track the status of its services [7].

Another company, **Amazon**, also actively uses microservices to manage a vast number of independent processes and services. They allow Amazon to efficiently distribute the load, automate deployment, and maintain a high level of fault tolerance [8].

Thus, the right choice of architectural solutions and the implementation of tools for automation and monitoring ensure high performance, reliability, and security of microservice systems, as confirmed by examples of successful implementations.

Conclusion

The analysis of architectural decisions, such as MA, demonstrates a significant impact on the performance of modern systems. Microservices provide high flexibility and scalability, allowing for independent deployment and development of individual system components. This is particularly important given the continuously growing demands for data processing and user interactions.

However, despite the obvious advantages such as independent development, horizontal scalability, and improved fault tolerance, MA also introduces additional complexities. These complexities involve managing network interactions, ensuring data consistency,

and the increased monitoring requirements. Architectural solutions aimed at minimizing network latency, optimizing inter-service communication, and load balancing play an important role in maintaining high performance. When properly implemented, with the use of modern automation, monitoring, and orchestration tools, MA can significantly enhance the performance and resilience of systems. It is crucial to consider these aspects when choosing an architecture for systems that require high performance, flexibility, and scalability.

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